

Structure of Benzylideneacetone - phenol Condensation Products

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The compound, $C_{22}H_{20}O_2$, obtained from phenol and benzylideneacetone, provides salicylic acid on alkali fusion and a cyclic ether, $C_{16}H_{16}O$, and a flavanone on oxidation with neutral $KMnO_4$ as also a trace of an acid. From these degradation products, a probable structure of the compound is suggested.

Salam and Ahmed¹ prepared a monohydroxy compound, $C_{22}H_{20}O_2$, by condensing phenol with benzylideneacetone in presence of hydrogen chloride. The compound was found to be formed from two moles of phenol and one mole of benzylideneacetone:

This paper reports further investigations on the structure of this compound.

The condensation product, $C_{22}H_{20}O_2$, gave salicylic acid on alkali fusion. On oxidation with neutral potassium permanganate, it afforded a cyclic ether, $C_{16}H_{16}O$, m.p. 135-36°, which did not yield any derivative with 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine. It was, however, soluble in sulphuric acid from which it could be recovered. Further, the infrared spectrum indicated the presence of a six-membered cyclic ether (peak at 1124 cm^{-1}). From the oxidation products, a flavanone (VII) was isolated. Besides, an acid of equivalent weight of 268 was also obtained.

The condensation of phenol with α,β -unsaturated carbonyl compounds in presence of acidic catalyst leads to the formation of a six-membered heterocyclic ring and takes place according to either the scheme A or the scheme B².

1. Salam and Ahmed, *Pak. J. Sci. Res.*, 1959, 11, 129.
2. Clayton *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 582.

In the light of the above views, the condensation product between one mole of phenol and one mole of benzylideneacetone would form either 2-methyl-4-phenylchromen-2 (III) following the scheme A or 2-phenyl-4-methylchromen-3 (IV) in accordance with the scheme B.

Subsequently the chromen-2 (III) may react further with another mole of phenol in presence of hydrogen chloride to afford (V), following the formation of 2-methoxy- or -ethoxy-4-phenylchroman in presence of methanolic or ethanolic hydrogen chloride² from 4-phenylchromen-2. Similarly, the subsequent condensation may involve the chromen-3 to form (VI) with another mole of phenol (cf. addition of phenol to 2,2,4-trimethylchromen³).

The presence of phenolic group, a $C-CH_3$ group, a six-membered cyclic ether, and an aromatic ring was indicated by the infrared spectrum, lending support to either of the structures (V) or (VI). Methylation study also revealed presence of one hydroxyl group.¹ Salicylic acid may be produced from both (V) and (VI). A choice between the structures (V) and (VI) is possible from the following consideration. The product affords flavanone (VII) which is possible only through (VI) and not (V), though a cyclic ether, $C_{16}H_{16}O$ (IX) or (XI), and an acid of equiv. 268 are possible from both the structures.

Formation of (VI) seems rather likely because it presupposes the addition of phenol to the cationoid β -carbon of the benzylideneacetone and such addition will be facilitated greatly in the acidic medium and by the presence of the electron-releasing⁴ phenyl group at the β -carbon.

EXPERIMENTAL

Benzylideneacetone-phenol Condensation Product.—The compound was prepared by following the method of Salem and Ahmed¹ by taking phenol (120 g.) and benzylideneacetone (30 g.). The product was crystallised from rectified spirit as stout white crystals, m.p. 222-23°. The infrared spectrum of the compound had the strong peaks at 3496 cm^{-1} , characteristic of the phenolic group⁵, at 1124 cm^{-1} , suggesting presence of a six-membered cyclic ether⁶, at 3012 cm^{-1} and 1524 cm^{-1} , indicating presence of aromatic ring⁷, at 1457 cm^{-1} , suggesting presence of C-(H₃ group)⁸. (Found: C, 83.18; H, 6.07. C₂₂H₂₀O₂ requires C, 83.53; H, 6.38%).

Fusion of the Condensation Product.—To the molten mass of KOH (30 g. in 5 ml) in a silver crucible was added in portions the product (5 g.); the temperature was maintained at 170-80° for 2 hours and at 250° for further 2 hours. The resultant brownish mass was cooled, dissolved in water, and extracted with ether (3 × 20 ml) after acidification with HCl (conc.). The ethereal solution was shaken with 5% NaOH solution (3 × 20 ml); The alkaline extract afforded on acidification a solid mass which, on treatment with charcoal in hot aqueous solution, yielded from water colorless needles, m.p. 155-56°. The m.p. remained undepressed on admixture with an authentic sample of salicylic acid. It gave a violet coloration with ferric chloride.

Oxidation of the Condensation Product.—The substance (3 g.) was dissolved in acetone (50 ml) containing a few crystals of ferrous sulphate in a two-litre flask fitted with an upright condenser and placed on a water bath. To the boiling solution was added a saturated solution of potassium permanganate in boiling acetone (900 ml) and the mixture refluxed for 30 mins. Acetone was then removed and the residue was shaken with water (100 ml), sodium pyrosulphite (20 g.), and 2N-HCl (40 ml). Through the mixture sulphur dioxide was passed until manganese dioxide dissolved. The solution was extracted with ether (3 × 50 ml) and the extract treated with 5% sodium bicarbonate solution (3 × 50 ml); the two layers were separated.

On slow evaporation of the ether layer, after two treatments with decolorising charcoal, white cylindrical crystals with white mass appeared. The crystals (VIII) were separated and recrystallised several times from ether, m.p. 135-36°. (Found: C, 85.45; H, 7.28; M.W., 223.3. C₁₆H₁₆O requires C, 85.26; H, 7.14%; M. W., 224). It is highly soluble in ether, acetone, and hot ethanol, fairly soluble in chloroform and cyclohexanol, but insoluble in water and alkali. It formed no 2,4-D.N.P; it gave negative ferric reaction

4. Barnett, "Mechanism of Organic Chemical Reactions", Blackie & Son Ltd., 1956, p. 27.

5. Bellamy, "The infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", John Wiley & Sons Inc., 1959, p. 87.

6. Shreve *et al.*, *Anal. Chem.*, 1951, 23, 277.

7. Ref. 5, p. 64.

8. Ref. 5, p. 13.

and it developed with H_2SO_4 (conc.) a red coloration from which the original compound was regenerated on dilution with water.

The white residue, left after separation of compound (VIII), was dissolved in ligroin. On slow evaporation, needle shaped crystals, m.p. 76° , were obtained (recorded⁹ m.p. of flavanone, 76°). It was further characterised by its benzylidene derivative, m.p. 103° (recorded⁹ m.p. 103°).

The bicarbonate solution on acidification with HCl (dil.) yielded a gummy mass which was extracted with ether. The ether extract, after treatment with decolorising charcoal, was extracted with 5% bicarbonate, acidified with HCl, and extracted with ether again. The process of addition of bicarbonate, followed by acidification and extraction, was repeated three times. Finally slow evaporation of ether yielded a colorless sticky mass which was dried in vacuum. This is soluble in ether, acetone, ethanol, and alkalies. (Found: Equiv. 268). The amount was too small for any additional work.

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